

THE ROLE OF OUR NATIONAL VALUES IN THE FAMILY

Datqayeva Feruza Ubaydullayevna

Andijan State Institute of pedagogy Direction "theory and methodology of education and training" Master of Stage 1
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8410154>

Annotation: the importance of the place of national values in the family, as well as the scope of their transmission and influence from generation to generation. The attitude and affection of the younger generation, coming of age in the family, towards him. Attention to national values in our homeland, ardor and show how important it is. This article covers values in the family about nationalism and attention to our national values.

Keywords: value and family, value that includes nationality, attitude, younger generation, Homeland, nationality, attention, ancestry

First of all, we will not be mistaken if we say that a number of valuable things that occupy the main place in our lives are actually those that cannot be seen with the eyes by hand. We can give them many examples, and we cannot deliver their definition in words at the base. Our national values are undoubtedly one of them. And his place in the family is an integral part of the family. There are several beautiful types of qadryts. Among them, the qadiriyats that our nationality has provided us are a wonderful treasure in the family, while his nationality has made us know who we are and how much our ancestors are can show that he is majestic and beautiful morals. Surely our ancestors were diligent in bringing them to the forefront of the growing younger generation so that they would not perish. It is possible to see right now that our national values can only and only positively influence the future generation. Because from our mothers we have studied and applied how to deal with those around us, from the etiquette and imagination of a girl child in the family, the attitude towards adults and young people, from the culture of dress to the sound achangi. And our grandfathers are brave to our young men and in Valor is a clear example in relationships such as respect for women. Therefore, the future generation that is born is loving our national values.

The preservation of national values in our homeland to this day, our compatriots continue to love all events held within the family, from folk holidays associated with our national values. One of these is definitely the Navruz holiday. If this holiday promotes harmony, harmony, ardor, hospitality, sumalak, which is also kept within our family in our national values in the spring season, gathered together with family or relatives and neighbors, is now an example of how much we love our Ham customs. It is fitting that these deeds are carried out in large numbers. Hotin-the fact that our girls are dressed in National Silk doppelgängers, satin and adras dresses, even makes other peoples envious. Surely it is a beautiful sight in the family that we still have enough attention to our nationality and dignity. Today, ham every household we see the Chakmas that our men use to wear, and each of our fellow countrymen uses them at weddings and various ceremonies. This also expresses our attitude and attention to our national values in our homeland and families today.

Our independence has re-introduced many national concepts into the way we live, together with our hurting to our country. Nowadays, the promotion of nationalism in the family the transformation of values into a habit has its own meaning VZ content. Including our previous and current Distinguished Presidents, Ham has a great service on this path. From the past, it is known that any people who want to depend on the path of the first person will go to the value, culture, national tradition of that people and nation- there will be a desire to deprive him of his habits, his past. If we do not repeat this every day, we have realized that our smallest national value in our family, country and society, Ham, has its important place. This cannot be denied. In fact, the language we speak is also a value. From generation to generation- the Uzbek language passed down to the generation is also the national value of our ruhidir. So ' we cannot lose our rising Psalms, we cannot forget, otherwise it is clear that we are in harmony with ourselves. Although this is an integral principle of our national value. The memory of our ancestors and traditions of our people, we keep forever in the net of our hearts. The eye rejoices to see that citizens and people of different nationalities living in harmony and living in our homeland for a long time will respect each other for their family values. The role of upbringing, absorbed in our blood and blood from our past, in this is further proven. There are countless traditions on earth, values of other peoples. Every man loves his nationality, pursues. The beaches and the K'oplab are in their own family and wherever other people from time to time go in love with the values in his homeland, he does not get tired and does not forget to tariff others. Even if it was sand. Young people of our time also come to live in many different countries nowadays because of their studies but we know that they also do not exchange our national dishes in the same place for other country dishes. People like pilaf, manti, qatlama, famous among our people, love yegulikar even in the distance. His parents maintain respect, affection for the rest of the family. This is also one of our sentences that we can proudly say among our young people to show how much our nationality is absorbed in them. Since our ancient history, these traditions have continued to massively add to our spirituality. Only the word etiquette itself does not give a man the ugliness. It is valuable that a person can show this in his attitude, and we can proudly say that this is one of those feelings, upbringing that is very well shaped in our national values. We introduce this into society by learning from adults in our family. As a result, we can show that we treat each other beautifully, in which national values have developed in our family.

In conclusion, it follows that family and national values are inherited in our past, in the way we live now, from ancestors to descendants. Surely in this family it means that our glory is attentive to our deeds, and in its place it pleases. We are obliged to constantly fulfill them with respect, instilling them in the mind, so that in the future young avlo they do not forget about national values or leave them out of sight, while remaining faithful to our achievements in the eyes of infancy. Zero family this is the first teacher.

References:

1. ISLOM KARIMOV MILLIY ISTIQLOL MAFKURASI-XALQ E'TIQODI VA BUYUK KELAJAKKA ISHONCHDIR. "FIDOKOR" gazetasi muhbiri savollariga javoblar. TOSHKENT - "O'ZBEKISTON"- 2000. 13 bet, 23 bet.
2. SHAVKAT MIRZIYOYEV ERKIN VA FAROVON DEMOKRATIK O'ZBEKISTON DAVLATINI BIRGALIKDA BARPO ETAMIZ. O'zbekiston Respublikasi Prezidenti lavozimiga kirishish

tantanali marosimiga bag'ishlangan Oliy majlis palatalarining qo'shma majlisidagi
nutq. TOSHKENT-"O'ZBEKISTON"-2016, 9 bet

3.XAMIDXON NABIYEV Qadriyatlarimiz bo'stoni. Ma'naviy-ma'rifiy mushohadalar
"Namangan" nashriyoti. 2004-yil, 20 bet, 30 bet.

4.J.Tulenov Milliy qadriyatlar va ijtimoiy taraqqiyot.TOSHKENT "O'ZBEKISTON"1999
yil.O'ZBEKISTON RESPUBLIKASI OLIY VA O'RTA MAXSUS TA'LIM VAZIRLIGI NIZOMIY
NOMIDAGI TOSHKENT DAVLAT PEDOGOGIKA UNIVERSITETI FALSAFA KAFERDASI.12 bet,19
bet.

